

Clinical Features of Periodontal Abscess as Potential Additional Screening Criteria for Diabetes Mellitus in Malaysia

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ABSTRACT

Background

Although periodontal abscess is recommended to be used to guide the screening for diabetes mellitus (DM), the information on their interactions is still limited. This study was designed to assess the relationship between the clinical features of periodontal abscess and the status and control of DM.

Methods

The medical records of all the patients with periodontal abscess, who presented to a periodontics specialist clinic in Northern Malaysia between 2014 and 2017, were examined. Their demographics and oral health status recorded. The information on the clinical features of periodontal abscess was also gathered. The DM status of patients was confirmed primarily based on their patient medical records, while uncontrolled DM was indicated by a random blood sugar $>11\text{mmol/L}$ or a HbA1c $>6.5\%$.

Results

Ninety-six patients with periodontal abscess were identified, with a total of 156 teeth involved. The proportion of Indian patients in the DM group was notably higher than that in the non-DM group ($p=0.03$). Poor oral hygiene ($p=0.03$), a higher number of teeth with periodontal abscess ($p=0.018$) and bleeding on probing at mesiolingual sites ($p=0.015$) were also significantly associated with the DM status of patients. Meantime, the presence of multirrooted teeth with furcation involvement was found to be associated with both the DM status ($p=0.039$) and control ($p=0.032$) of patients.

Conclusion

The factors identified to be associated with DM and its control in this study could be helpful in the identification of high-risk group of the disease more effectively, which is essential to ensure timely treatment.

Keywords: Periodontal abscess, Diabetes mellitus, Screening criteria, Poor oral hygiene, Multiple abscess, Furcation involvement

Introduction

Periodontal abscess is a localized purulent infection within the periodontal tissues. It is caused by the inflammatory reaction against pathogens in dental plaques, which eventually leads to the accumulation of purulent exudate in the periodontal pockets.¹ Without timely treatment, tooth loss could occur following the rapid destruction of periodontal ligaments and alveolar bones.²

Periodontitis is one of the common causes of periodontal abscess, especially in tortuous pockets with cul-de-sacs.^{3,4} Other possible causes of periodontal abscess include inadequate scaling, periodontal treatment with systemic antibiotics without subgingival debridement, periodontal surgery, impaction of foreign bodies, occlusal trauma and endodontic infection.⁵⁻¹³ Diabetes mellitus (DM) could also alter the nature of the inflammatory response and subsequently result in periodontal abscess due to the compromised defense mechanism.^{14,15} The association between DM and periodontal abscess is also particularly strong in uncontrolled DM cases, often characterized by multiple abscess, recurrence and a poor response to treatment.^{16,17} Interestingly, such a relationship is also proposed to be bidirectional.^{18,19} It is postulated that pro-inflammatory cytokines released from gingiva could exacerbate DM.²⁰ Therefore, periodontal abscess has been recommended to guide screening for DM.¹⁷

In Malaysia, the information on periodontal abscess and how it has been interacting with DM is still limited. Currently, approximately 10% of Malaysians have undiagnosed DM.²¹ As periodontal abscess has different clinical features across patients, a better understanding of the relationship between these features and DM can potentially provide more specific screening criteria for the disease.^{3,16,17} While the burden of DM management falls mainly on public health institutions in Malaysia, the objective of this study aimed to assess the associations between the clinical features of periodontal abscess and the status of DM, as well as its relationship with the control of DM, among the patients seeking treatment in a public periodontics specialist clinic.

Methods

This cross-sectional study was undertaken at the Department of Periodontics of the Datuk Kumbar Clinic, which serves as one of the referral centers for advanced and refractory periodontal diseases in northern Malaysia. The study protocol was registered with the National Medical Research Register (NMRR-18-242-39561), and was approved by the Medical Research and Ethics Committee.

All the patients in the age range of 18 to 80 years, who presented to the clinic with periodontal abscess between 2014 and 2017, were included in the study. On the other hand, the patients, who were found to have factors potentially altering the nature of inflammatory response to plaque were excluded from the study. Such factors included having systemic diseases other than DM, smoking, pregnancy, having traumatic teeth and having had received any treatment for periodontal diseases from the clinic.^{6-10,12,13}

Data collection

Patient-Based Data

The complete list of the eligible patients was obtained from the Patient Registration Book of the clinic. The demographic data collected included age, gender and race. The information on the individual oral health status, including full mouth plaque score (FMPS), percentages of teeth with probing pocket depth (PPD) ≥ 4 mm and ≥ 6 mm, the number of missing teeth, the number of teeth with periodontal abscess and the number of other teeth with suppuration, were also recorded. FMPS was categorized into three groups: good (<20%), fair (21-40%) and poor (>40%).²² The number of sites with PPD ≥ 4 mm was also dichotomized into <30% and >30%.²³ Meanwhile, the number of sites with PPD ≥ 6 mm and missing teeth were grouped by into 5-teeth intervals.²⁴ The information on the DM status of patients was obtained from the Confidential Medical Questionnaire (CMQ) or their patient medical records. Uncontrolled DM was indicated by a random blood sugar (RBS) level >11mmol/L or a HbA1c level >6.5% in 3 months preceding the clinic visit as suggested by Malaysia Clinical Practice Guidelines.^{25,26}

Tooth-Based Data

The data for clinical features of periodontal abscess, ranging from the involved teeth, clinical attachment loss (CAL), tooth mobility grading, ovoid gingival elevation, the number of multirrooted teeth with furcation involvement to sites of suppuration and bleeding on probing (BOP), were also gathered. The involved teeth were grouped into 6 sextants as recommended by the Basic Periodontal Examination guidelines;²⁷ while the CAL was classified into “mild” (1-2mm), “moderate” (3-4mm) and “severe” (≥ 5 mm).²³

Statistical analysis

The data was analyzed by using the SPSS for Windows version 23 (IBM, New York). The categorical data was presented as frequencies and percentages and the numerical data as medians and interquartile ranges. Pearson’s Chi-Square test and Fisher’s exact test were then used to assess the associations between the DM status and the characteristics of patients and their teeth, while Mann-Whitney test was used to assess the differences in the number of missing teeth, as well as in the number of teeth with periodontal abscess between the DM and non-DM groups. All the statistical tests were two-tailed, with the significant level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Of the 96 patients with periodontal abscess presenting to the clinic during the study period, 25 (26%) had DM. Most patients in both the DM and non-DM groups were aged between 40 and 59 years. The majority of the DM patients with periodontal abscess were Malay, and the proportion of Indian patients in the DM group was relatively high as compared with the non-DM group ($p = 0.03$). Those with a poor oral hygiene, based on the plaque score, also had a higher tendency of being diagnosed with DM ($p = 0.03$). The DM group also had a higher median number of teeth with periodontal abscess (2; interquartile range (IQR) = 1) than did the non-diabetic group (1; IQR = 1) ($p = 0.018$). Nevertheless, the diabetes status did not vary across the number of sites with PPD ≥ 4 mm and ≥ 6 mm, the number of missing teeth and the number of other teeth with suppuration. (Table 1).

Table I. Demographics and general oral health by diabetic status of patients (n=96).

	Diabetes (n=25), n (%)	Non-diabetes (n=71), n (%)	P-value
Age(years)^a			0.678
≤29	2 (8.0)	6 (8.5)	
30-39	4 (16.0)	16 (22.5)	
40-49	7 (28.0)	25 (35.2)	
50-59	7 (28.0)	17 (23.9)	
≥60	5 (20.0)	7 (9.9)	
Gender^a			0.575
Male	10 (40.0)	33 (46.5)	
Female	15 (60.0)	38 (53.5)	
Ethnicity^b			0.030
Malay	19 (76.0)	52 (73.2)	
Chinese	2 (8.0)	17 (23.9)	
Indian	3 (12.0)	2 (2.8)	
Others	1 (4.0)	0 (0)	
Full Mouth Plaque score^a			0.030
Good (<20%)	1 (4.0)	10 (14.1)	
Fair (21-40%)	9 (36.0)	39 (54.9)	
Poor (>40%)	15 (60.0)	22 (31.0)	
Number of sites with Probing pocket depth ≥4mm^a			0.165
<30%	9 (36.0)	37 (52.1)	
≥30%	16 (64.0)	34 (47.9)	
Number of sites with Probing pocket depth ≥6mm^b			0.348
≤5	8 (33.3)	34 (43.1)	
6-10	7 (29.2)	13 (20.0)	
11-15	7 (25.0)	9 (13.8)	
16-20	2 (8.3)	6 (9.2)	
21-25	1 (4.2)	7 (10.8)	
>25	0 (0.0)	2 (3.1)	
Number of missing teeth^b			0.892
0	4 (12.5)	10 (12.5)	
1-5	13 (58.3)	41 (56.3)	
6-10	4 (12.5)	9 (14.1)	
11-15	2 (8.3)	8 (12.5)	
>15	2 (8.3)	3 (4.7)	
Median (interquartile range) ^c	3 (7)	4 (5)	0.938
Number of teeth with periodontal abscess^b			0.051
1	10 (40.0)	47 (66.2)	
2	11 (44.0)	20 (28.2)	
≥3	4 (16.0)	4 (5.6)	
Median (interquartile range) ^c	2 (1)	1 (1)	0.018
Number of other teeth with suppuration^b			0.603
Yes	2 (8.0)	3 (4.2)	
No	23 (92.0)	68 (95.8)	

a-Pearson's chi square test; b-Fisher's exact test; c- Mann-Whitney test

Approximately 30% of the 156 teeth involved were from the DM patients. As compared with the non-diabetic group, a higher proportion (65.5%) of multirooted teeth were found to have furcation involvement in the diabetic group (65.5% vs 41.8%; $p=0.039$). BOP at the mesiolingual sites of the teeth was also found to be more common among the DM patients (84.8% vs 65.5%) ($p=0.015$). However, the teeth of the DM and non-DM groups did not differ in their CAL, tooth mobility grading, ovoid gingival elevation and suppuration ($p>0.05$) (Table 2).

Table II. Clinical features of periodontal abscess by diabetic status of patients (n=96).

	Diabetes (n=25), n (%)	Non-diabetes (n=71), n (%)	P-value
Involved sextant^b			0.139
1 st sextant	13 (28.3)	12 (10.9)	
2 nd sextant	6 (13.0)	16 (14.5)	
3 rd sextant	8 (17.4)	19 (17.3)	
4 th sextant	2 (4.3)	5 (4.5)	
5 th sextant	7 (15.2)	30 (27.3)	
6 th sextant	10 (21.7)	28 (25.5)	
Age(years)^a			0.280
≤29	3 (6.5)	8 (7.3)	
30-39	8 (17.4)	25 (22.7)	
40-49	10 (21.7)	36 (32.7)	
50-59	17 (37.0)	23 (20.9)	
≥60	8 (17.4)	18 (16.4)	
Gender^a			0.011
Male	14 (30.4)	58 (52.7)	
Female	32 (69.6)	52 (47.3)	
Ethnicity^b			0.024
Malay	38 (82.6)	90 (81.8)	
Chinese	3 (6.5)	18 (16.4)	
Indian	4 (8.7)	2 (1.8)	
Others	1 (2.2)	0 (0.0)	
Clinical attachment loss^b			0.283
Mild (1-2mm)	0 (0.0)	2 (1.9)	
Moderate (3-4mm)	2 (4.3)	1 (0.9)	
Severe (≥5)	44 (95.7)	105 (97.2)	
Tooth mobility grading^b			0.234
No mobility	17 (37.0)	35 (32.4)	
Grade I	8 (17.4)	30 (27.8)	
Grade II	12 (26.1)	16 (14.8)	
Grade III	9 (19.6)	27 (25.0)	
Ovoid gingival elevation^b			0.733
Yes	42 (91.3)	103 (93.6)	
No	4 (8.7)	7 (6.4)	
Number of multirooted teeth with			0.039

Furcation involvement^{a*} (n=84)			
Yes	19 (65.5)	23 (41.8)	
No	10 (34.5)	32 (58.2)	
Suppuration sites			
Mesiobuccal^b			>0.95
Yes	9 (19.6)	21 (19.1)	
No	37 (80.4)	89 (80.9)	
Midbuccal^b			0.192
Yes	25 (54.3)	72 (65.5)	
No	21 (45.7)	38 (34.5)	
Distobuccal^a			0.323
Yes	11 (23.9)	35 (31.8)	
No	35 (76.1)	75 (68.2)	
Mesiolingual^b			0.724
Yes	2 (4.3)	8 (7.3)	
No	44 (95.7)	102 (92.7)	
Midlingual^b			0.914
Yes	7 (15.2)	16 (14.5)	
No	39 (84.8)	94 (85.5)	
Distolingual^a			0.283
Yes	1 (2.2)	8 (7.3)	
No	45 (97.8)	102 (92.7)	
Bleeding on probing sites			
Mesiobuccal^a			0.184
Yes	36 (78.3)	74 (67.3)	
No	10 (21.7)	36 (32.7)	
Midbuccal^a			0.328
Yes	29 (63.0)	60 (54.5)	
No	17 (37.0)	50 (45.5)	
Distobuccal^a			0.092
Yes	36 (78.3)	71 (64.5)	
No	10 (21.7)	39 (35.5)	
Mesiolingual^a			0.015
Yes	39 (84.8)	72 (65.5)	
No	7 (15.2)	38 (34.5)	
Midlingual^a			0.051
Yes	34 (73.9)	63 (57.3)	
No	12 (26.1)	47 (42.7)	
Distolingual^a			0.179
Yes	34 (73.9)	69 (62.7)	
No	12 (26.1)	41 (37.3)	

a-Pearson's chi square test; b-Fisher's exact test

* Only multirooted teeth were computed.

Approximately 70% of the 46 teeth involved in the DM group belonged to those who had a controlled blood glucose or HbA1C level. A sub-analysis on the teeth involved in the DM patients showed that the presence of multirooted teeth with furcation involvement was more commonly found in those who had their blood glucose or HbA1C levels under control ($p=0.032$). (Table 3)

Table III. Clinical features of periodontal abscess by control of diabetes of patients (n=46).

	Controlled (n=32), n (%)	Uncontrolled (n=14), n (%)	P-value
Involved sextant^b			0.203
1 st sextant	10 (31.3)	3 (21.4)	
2 nd sextant	6 (18.8)	0 (0.0)	
3 rd sextant	4 (12.5)	4 (28.6)	
4 th sextant	2 (6.3)	0 (0.0)	
5 th sextant	3 (9.4)	4 (28.6)	
6 th sextant	7 (21.9)	3 (21.4)	
Age(years)^b			0.793
≤29	1 (3.1)	2 (14.3)	
30-39	6 (18.8)	2 (14.3)	
40-49	7 (21.9)	3 (21.4)	
50-59	12 (37.5)	5 (35.7)	
≥60	6 (18.8)	2 (14.3)	
Gender^b			0.731
Male	9 (28.1)	5 (35.7)	
Female	23 (71.9)	9 (64.3)	
Ethnicity^b			0.865
Malay	25 (78.1)	13 (92.9)	
Chinese	3 (9.4)	0 (0.0)	
Indian	3 (9.4)	1 (7.1)	
Others	1 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	
Clinical attachment loss^b			0.088
Mild (1-2mm)	-	-	
Moderate (3-4mm)	0 (0.0)	2 (14.3)	
Severe (≥5)	32 (100.0)	12 (85.7)	
Tooth mobility^b			0.659
No mobility	11 (34.4)	7 (42.9)	
Grade I	7 (21.9)	1 (7.1)	
Grade II	8 (25.0)	4 (28.6)	
Grade III	6 (18.8)	2 (21.4)	
Ovoid gingival elevation^b			0.574
Yes	30 (93.8)	12 (85.7)	
No	2 (6.3)	2 (14.3)	
Number of multirooted teeth with Furcation^{a*} (n=29)			0.032
Yes	16 (80.0)	3 (33.3)	
No	4 (20.0)	6 (66.7)	
Suppuration sites			
Mesiobuccal ^b			>0.95

Yes	6 (18.8)	3 (21.4)	
No	26 (81.3)	11 (78.6)	
<i>Midbuccal</i> ^a			0.371
Yes	16 (50.0)	9 (64.3)	
No	16 (50.0)	2 (35.7)	
<i>Distobuccal</i> ^b			0.713
Yes	7 (21.9)	4 (28.6)	
No	25 (78.1)	10 (71.4)	
<i>Mesiolingual</i> ^b			>0.95
Yes	2 (6.3)	0 (0.0)	
No	30 (93.8)	14 (100.0)	
<i>Midlingual</i> ^b			>0.95
Yes	5 (15.6)	2 (14.3)	
No	27 (84.4)	12 (85.7)	
<i>Distolingual</i> ^b			>0.95
Yes	1 (3.1)	0 (0.0)	
No	31 (96.9)	14 (100.0)	
Bleeding on probing sites			
<i>Mesiobuccal</i> ^b			0.699
Yes	24 (75.0)	12 (85.7)	
No	8 (25.0)	2 (14.3)	
<i>Midbuccal</i> ^a			0.908
Yes	20 (62.5)	9 (64.3)	
no	12 (37.5)	5 (35.7)	
<i>Distobuccal</i> ^b			0.699
Yes	24 (75.0)	12 (85.7)	
No	8 (25.0)	2 (14.3)	
<i>Mesiolingual</i> ^b			0.083
Yes	25 (78.1)	14 (100.0)	
no	7 (21.9)	0 (0.0)	
<i>Midlingual</i> ^b			0.729
Yes	23 (71.9)	11 (78.6)	
No	9 (28.1)	3 (21.4)	
<i>Distolingual</i> ^b			0.294
Yes	22 (68.8)	12 (85.7)	
No	10 (31.3)	2 (14.3)	

a-Pearson's chi square test; b-Fisher's exact test

* Only multirooted teeth were computed.

Discussion

Our study suggests that the DM status and control of patients with periodontal abscess are associated with a few of their demographic and clinical characteristics. Such findings can potentially help dentists identify the high-risk group of DM and poorly controlled DM patients more effectively. Consequently, the patients could be referred for DM management timely.

Although more than 70% the patients seeking treatment in this study were Malays, the proportion of the Malay patients did not notably differ between the DM and non-DM groups. Yet, ethnicity was found to be significantly associated with the DM status of the patients with periodontal abscess. It is shown that the DM group had a higher proportion of Indian patients than did the non-DM group. In addition to lifestyle, Indians have been reported to be more susceptible to insulin resistance and beta cell dysfunction in general.^{28,29} As a result, the altered inflammatory response might have predisposed them to a higher risk of periodontal destruction. Against the background of limited resources across the public healthcare facilities, a strategy to promote the screening for DM among the patients with periodontal abscess which takes account of the ethnic differences in susceptibility to the disease is, therefore, warranted.

While a proper toothbrushing technique is crucial in preventing periodontal diseases, it is also noteworthy that diabetes was often shown to be present concurrently with a poor oral hygiene among the patients with periodontal abscess in this study. This was likely attributable to the increased glucose level in the saliva and gingival crevicular fluid, which had provided an ideal environment for proliferation of plaque pathogens.^{30,31} Meanwhile, this study also suggests that the mesiolingual sites of the teeth with periodontal abscess underwent a greater degree of plaque-induced gingival inflammation, which was indicated by BOP. Although it has been reported that interproximal (mesial and distal) and lingual sites could exhibit greater plaque accumulation,³²⁻³⁴ mesiolingual sites were likely be used more commonly to detect gingival inflammation, especially when it is exaggerated by the altered immune response.

DM patients were also found to generally have a higher number of teeth presenting with periodontal abscess. Due to the compromised defense mechanism and increased susceptibility to infections, it is likely that multiple teeth are predisposed to rapid periodontal breakdown regardless of the amount of dental plaque.³⁵ This was particularly more common in patients with uncontrolled DM.^{16,17} Dentists should be alert of the presentation of multiple periodontal abscess without obvious causes, as this could be indicative of the presence of underlying DM.

Furthermore, multirooted teeth with furcation involvement were more commonly seen in DM patients, particularly when the disease was uncontrolled. It has been reported that these patients could have greater periodontal destruction, which in turn results in furcation involvement.^{30,36,37} However, the previous studies focused mainly on the association of DM with periodontitis rather than periodontal abscess. Nonetheless, the etiopathogeneses of these two conditions are believed to be rather similar.^{3,38} Although uncontrolled blood glucose and HbA1C levels can potentially accelerate periodontal breakdown,³⁹ the incidence of multirooted teeth furcation involvement was shown to be higher in the patients with controlled DM in this study. It was possible that similar cases in the patients with uncontrolled DM were unrecorded, as the teeth involved were extracted due to dental caries. While the presence of multirooted teeth with furcation involvement could be used to help in the screening of underlying DM, their relationship with the control of DM remains uncertain.

Limitation

The conclusiveness of the relationship between ethnicity and the DM status of patients with periodontal abscess could be limited by the relatively small sample size in certain ethnic groups. This study was also limited by not taking account of radiological findings, particularly of periapical or bitewing radiograph, as marginal bone loss was shown to be related to DM.⁴⁰

Conclusion

This study shows that ethnicity, oral hygiene, number of teeth with periodontal abscess, sites of BOP and number of multirooted teeth with furcation involvement are significantly associated with the DM status of the patients with periodontal abscess. These findings could assist in the identification of high-risk group of DM more effectively, and they are essential to ensure timely treatment. However, despite the positive correlation between DM status and the number of multirooted teeth with furcation involvement, its relationship with control of DM is still inconclusive. Large-scale prospective studies are therefore required to investigate further, as well as other factors which are potentially associated with DM.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank the Director General of Health Malaysia for his permission to publish this article. The authors would also like to extend their gratitude to the Department of Periodontics in Kota Setar for allowing conducting the research.

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